

Time-Aware Retrieval for Question Answering over Streaming Data

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Abstract. Despite the successes of generation systems equipped with an “external memory” (RAG), a critical problem remains the disregard for the temporal context of documents. Traditional semantic search methods do not distinguish between historical and current information, which leads to chronological errors — the mixing of outdated data with relevant data and the incorrect interpretation of the temporal parameters of a query. This work proposes a solution aimed at introducing mechanisms for assessing the temporal relevance of answers. The approach is based on the development of a relevance scoring system that analyzes time markers in documents, matching them against the time interval in the user’s query. The proposed method makes it possible to effectively filter conflicting information and prioritize data corresponding to the requested time period. Experimental validation confirms that introducing a relevance-assessment block increases the accuracy of answers for time-dependent questions for two versions of the system: the temporally static version, where accuracy was evaluated on a fixed set of temporal questions and a fully indexed set of documents, and the temporally dynamic version, where evaluation on a set of questions was performed under continuous loading and updating of documents.

Keywords: RAG · stream processing · temporal embeddings · indexing

1 Introduction

In the modern artificial intelligence industry, retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) technology has become a standard for improving large language models (LLMs) by retrieving external knowledge in real time [1]. This approach is critically important, since even the most modern models demonstrate broad capabilities but remain limited by the scope of the data on which they were trained [2]. Although transformer-type architectures allow models to learn from a few examples (few-shot learning) [3], and effective open solutions such as Llama [4] are built on their basis, the problem of knowledge relevance remains acute. Even advanced systems that use reinforcement learning for reasoning, such as DeepSeek [5] or Qwen3 [6], are not immune to providing outdated information if they do not access an up-to-date database. The use of RAG makes it possible to significantly reduce the level of hallucinations in dialogue systems [7]. To further

increase accuracy, specialized model-tuning pipelines have been developed that account for the risk of hallucinations during generation [8], as well as methods for the systematic injection of knowledge in specific domains [9]. However, one of the problems that remains is that in standard RAG the relevance of a document is determined by the similarity of vectors in the vector space. Semantically similar documents may contain directly opposite facts because of the difference in the time of their creation. RAG is unable to interpret relative time references in a user’s query (for example, “in the last quarter”, “the latest changes”, “yesterday”, etc.) and, as a consequence, cannot trace the “evolution” of an object over time, without accounting for the order in which events occur.

This is confirmed by recent studies of the impact of “stale” information on answer quality [10]. Modern attempts to solve the retrieval problem include graph-based approaches (Graph RAG) [11]. However, correct answers to time-sensitive questions require specialized datasets and metrics [12]. Moreover, it is necessary to develop mechanisms for reasoning over temporal knowledge graphs with dynamic memory augmentation [13], since traditional information retrieval in its current form still does not sufficiently account for temporal specificity [14]. This work considers two configurations of the RAG system, differing in the mode by which documents arrive in the database:

- the temporally static system — a configuration in which evaluation is performed on a fixed set of questions and a pre-formed, fully indexed array of documents. This configuration does not entail any change to the knowledge base during the evaluation of the system.
- the temporally dynamic system — a configuration in which the processing of questions occurs under conditions of the continuous arrival of new data. It assumes constant updating of documents, which requires the system to account for the relevance of information in real time.

The method described in this article allows the model not merely to find similar documents but also to determine how relevant the proposed answer is to the current query, thereby eliminating the mixing of outdated and current data. To evaluate the results, three main hypotheses are put forward:

- Hypothesis No. 1. Using simultaneously all the methods presented in the study for the temporally static system will make it possible to increase query accuracy (accuracy and temporal accuracy) with an insignificant increase in query processing time (latency).
- Hypothesis No. 2. Using filtering in the temporally static system, by cutting off unnecessary documents, will make it possible to use fewer input-context tokens for the generator model when generating an answer.
- Hypothesis No. 3. Using all the methods in the study of the temporally dynamic system will make it possible to significantly improve the quality metrics (future leakage rate, staleness rate, mean temporal error) for this system.

2 Related Work

2.1 The Need to Account for Data Relevance in LLMs

The study of temporal data in question-answering (TQA) tasks is foundational to this work. The correct operation of a TQA system depends on two key factors: the understanding of temporal relations and the retrieval of knowledge with regard to the time factor. Understanding relations includes the interpretation of dates, durations, and connections of the type “before”, “after”, or “during” [15], [16]. The main problem of LLMs is that they are trained on static datasets, which renders their knowledge outdated immediately after the completion of training. Although continual fine-tuning can update a model’s knowledge base, this process is computationally expensive and carries the risk of forgetting previously learned information [17]. This makes the RAG paradigm a more flexible and preferable solution.

2.2 Datasets and Benchmarks for Temporal Analysis

Many datasets have been developed to assess progress in the field of TQA. Early works, such as TempQuestions [18], laid the foundation for working with explicit and implicit time markers. Subsequent datasets were aimed at solving more complex scenarios, such as working with different temporal relations in knowledge graphs (MULTITQ and others) [19], [20]. Particular attention was paid to questions requiring reasoning over facts that change over time (TimeQA) [21], and to the analysis of long-term historical newspaper archives [22]. To test the ability of models to adapt to a stream of new information, StreamingQA was proposed [23]. This work will consider methods of accounting for temporal relevance on a continuous stream of information loaded into the storage. The work [24] contains a dataset (TempRAGEval), the questions and time markers from which were used for this study.

3 Methodology

The proposed approach to implementing a time-dependent RAG system is based on a two-stage data processing: (1) enriching documents with temporal metadata at the indexing stage and (2) hybrid ranking that accounts for temporal relevance during retrieval.

3.1 Server Setup

The experiments are conducted on a remote server in an isolated container with the following specifications:

Operating system: Ubuntu 24.04.2 LTS (Noble Numbat)

Processor: AMD EPYC 9124 — 2 units (32 physical cores in total)

Graphics card: NVIDIA RTX 6000 Ada Generation — 2 units (96 GB of GDDR6 video memory in total)

3.2 System Architecture

The general scheme of the pipeline includes the extraction of time markers using a large language model (LLM) and the subsequent use of these markers. Unlike classical systems, in this method there occurs not only the retrieval of semantically close documents but also the matching of the query time interval T_q with the context time interval T_c , which makes it possible to perform advanced filtering based on the comparison of temporal values.

The application has a modular architecture, which makes it possible to replace various elements of the system, such as the loading and processing of datasets, the tokenizer, the vector database, and the LLM for text processing (through the use of the OpenAI API), in accordance with best practices for building application architectures, and as a consequence makes it possible to quickly add various methods and metrics to the pipeline.

Large Language Models

The work uses several large language models in order to separate the logic of data extraction and answer generation. Model hosting — LiteLLM

Dataset

For both systems, a combination of two datasets was used.

To conduct the experiments, a dataset for RAG evaluation is required, containing time-dependent questions and the following fields: question, answer, context, correct answer time. The TempRAGEval dataset meets this criterion.

A feature of this dataset is the presence of several versions of the same question with different time periods, which is ideally suited for the study of temporal relevance. A major drawback is the absence of context documents for a given question. To solve this problem, it was necessary to use another dataset, from which the authors of the TempRAGEval dataset took exactly half of the questions. And only this half will be used to conduct all the experiments in this work.

The dataset containing context documents for the questions is TimeQA (the ‘test’ subset). The number of examples is $\sim 40,000$.

Extraction of Temporal Data

One of the main components of the system is a large language model that performs the function of extracting time markers from text. Zero-shot/few-shot learning methods are used, allowing time markers to be obtained in a given structured format, ISO 8601. In cases where it is necessary to extract time intervals from a user’s query containing relative time references (for example, “in the current year”), the system first normalizes them into absolute values relative to the date on which the query was made. Thus, the obtained time markers make it possible to perform filtering using algorithmic methods.

Vector Store

The selected vector database — Qdrant — makes it possible to store large volumes of data on disk, process them quickly, and also perform filtering by metadata, which makes it possible to conduct a variety of experiments with the retrieval of information from the database. The dimensionality of the vector space is 384 dimensions (tokenizer — MiniLM-L6-v2). Cosine similarity is used to find relevant documents. The minimum document retrieval score during search and the top-k documents vary depending on the experiment.

Quality Metrics

A set of metrics is used to evaluate the systems. The formulas for their calculation are given in the sections where they are directly applied.

The answer-correctness metrics are implemented by means of queries to large language models, since the accuracy of an answer with regard to date is difficult to measure with lexical and semantic metrics.

The temporal accuracy metric represents a comparison of two time intervals: the time interval of the correct answer and the time interval created by the generator when forming the answer. The generator’s prompt specifies that the time marker for the answer must be based on the same documents on which the answer was based. These time markers are then passed to the judge model without indicating the produced answer and the correct answer. This allows the judge model to base its decision strictly on the comparison of time markers without confusion with the semantic answer.

3.3 Study of the Temporally Static System

In this section, studies were conducted on ways of accounting for temporal context for a static set of documents that is unchanged over time and for queries containing requirements to produce an answer at a specific historical moment.

Quality Metrics for Studying Answer Accuracy on a Given Dataset

Four metrics are used to evaluate the answers:

- Accuracy LLM-as-a-Judge (accuracy):

$$\text{Accuracy}_{\{LLM\}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N S_i, \quad S_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (1)$$

where S_i is the binary assessment of the relevance of the answer for the i -th query, determined using an LLM;

N is the total number of queries.

- Temporal accuracy LLM-as-a-Judge (temporal accuracy):

$$\text{Temp. accuracy}_{\{LLM\}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} S_{t_i}, \quad S_{t_i} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (2)$$

where S_{t_i} is the binary assessment of the relevance of the answer time for the i -th query, determined using an LLM.

- **Acc@k**: a retrieval quality metric that determines whether a relevant document fell within the first k produced documents:

$$\text{Acc@}k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{J}(\text{rank}_i \leq k), \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{J} is the indicator function, equal to 1 if the true document is found in the top- k , and 0 otherwise;

rank_i is the position of the relevant document in the search results for the i -th query;

- **Latency** (query processing time):

$$L_{\{\text{avg}\}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta t_i \quad (4)$$

where Δt_i is the total processing time of the i -th query;

Baseline Version of the System

The baseline version is the simplest RAG pipeline. After indexing the documents from TimeQA, evaluation is launched on the TempRAGEval dataset.

Version with Temporal Augmentation

A feature of this modification is the change in the input context for the generator: to each text fragment, an extracted marker is forcibly added by means of another model responsible for extracting temporal entities, in the format of XML markup, for the model’s more convenient understanding of the boundaries of documents and dates:

```
<document id="1"> [Document text], Intervals:[...] </document>
```

This allows the model, when producing an answer, to immediately pay attention to the time markers of a given document.

Version with a Hard Filtering Mechanism

At this stage of extracting temporal entities, a hard filtering block is introduced into the system. This mechanism is intended to cut off documents that obviously do not correspond to the temporal context of the user’s query.

The filtering process is based on comparing the extracted query time interval T_q and the time intervals in the document T_c . A document remains in the selection for further ranking only if the time interval from the user’s query T_q fully or partially falls within one of the document’s several time intervals. That is, if the set-intersection condition is satisfied:

$$f_{\text{filter}}(d_i) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } T_q \cap T_c \neq \emptyset \\ 0, & \text{if } T_q \cap T_c = \emptyset \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where d_i is the i -th candidate document for filtering;
 T_q is the extracted query time interval;
 T_c is the extracted time intervals from the document.

3.4 Study of the Temporally Dynamic System

In this section, a simulation of the data update stream is carried out by modifying documents already stored in the database that have time markers and by slightly changing the text of the document itself.

When loading and updating documents in the database, five parameters are used that allow the system to manage chronology:

- `id` — the document identifier. It makes it possible to update a document while preserving the previous version as a historical fact;
- `key_time` — a parameter responsible for the time associated with the correct answer. It is contained in the `key_time` field for each element of the TempRAGEval dataset;
- T_d — the document indexing time during the simulation of the update stream. Initially it is taken as `key_time`, and then it is changed by a fixed amount, signifying the arrival of a new document in the database and the need to update the stored values for that document;
- $L(d)$ (`is_latest`) — a Boolean flag showing whether a given document is the latest for a given `id`;
- t_s — the current simulation time.

The evaluation procedure is carried out with a fixed step on the full set of questions from the TempRAGEval dataset. In each evaluation procedure, time is frozen and new documents stop arriving. This makes it possible to track how the accumulation of old versions of documents affects the accuracy of retrieving current facts.

Temporal Relevance Metrics in the Context of the Data Update Stream

- **Future Leakage Rate.** This metric determines the proportion of documents in the retriever’s selection whose indexing time T_d exceeds the current simulation

time t_s . A high value of this metric indicates a violation of cause-and-effect relationships.

$$\text{FLR} = \frac{1}{|Q| \cdot k} \sum_{q \in Q} \sum_{d \in D_q} \mathcal{J}(T_d > t_s), \quad (6)$$

where Q is the set of test queries;

D_q is the subset of k documents retrieved for query q ;

$\mathcal{J}(T_d > t_s)$ is the indicator function, taking the value 1 if the condition is true.

- **Staleness Rate.** The metric reflects the proportion of non-current (outdated) documents in the context when fresher versions are present in the database. For questions that do not contain an explicit time reference (queries about the “current” state), the inclusion of a document with the flag `is_latest = false`, when an analogue with `is_latest = true` exists, is considered a staleness error.

$$\text{SR} = \frac{1}{|Q| \cdot k} \sum_{q \in Q} \sum_{d \in D_q} \mathcal{J}(L(d) = \text{false}). \quad (7)$$

- **Mean Temporal Error.** It is computed as the mean absolute difference, in years, between the time T_q extracted from the question and the actual creation/validity time of the document T_d . This metric makes it possible to assess the “fuzziness” of the temporal search: the lower the value, the more precisely the system selects documents for a specific historical period.

$$\text{MTE} = \frac{1}{|Q| \cdot k} \sum_{q \in Q} \sum_{d \in D_q} |T_q - T_d|. \quad (8)$$

Baseline Version of the Data Update Simulation Without Accounting for Data Temporal Relevance

The goal of this stage is to record the level of errors that arise under a constant stream of updating data.

Version of the Data Update Simulation Accounting for Data Temporal Relevance Through the Use of a Hard Filter and a Relevance Function

This version differs in its use of a hard filter that cuts off documents by the `is_latest` flag or by a mismatch in document availability (the query contains a question about a future time)

After the initial selection of the top- k documents by the cosine similarity of vectors (S_{sem}) and the performance of hard filtering, a relevance score S_{total} is computed for each document:

$$S_{total} = w_1 \cdot S_{sem} + w_2 \cdot S_{temp}, \quad (9)$$

where:

- S_{sem} — semantic similarity;
- S_{temp} — temporal similarity;
- w_1, w_2 — weighting coefficients that determine the priority of relevance, selected empirically.

The temporal score S_{temp} is computed based on the time difference between the interval T_q extracted from the question (or a point date) and the document's time marker T_d for historical queries.

$$S_{temp} = \begin{cases} -\infty, & \text{if } T_d > t_s \\ \exp\left(-\frac{(T_q - T_d)^2}{\sigma}\right), & \text{if } T_d < t_s \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where:

- T_q — the extracted query time
- T_d — the document loading time
- σ — a coefficient that determines the decay sensitivity
- t_s — the current simulation time

Adopted Baseline

As the baseline configuration for the temporally dynamic system, a solution is considered that combines hard filtering by metadata with ranking based on the Reciprocal Rank Fusion (RRF) method. This version was chosen as the baseline because it reflects a common approach to hybrid search, in which the temporal component is accounted for indirectly — through the combination of several ranked lists.

At the filtering stage, the same cut-off mechanism is applied as in the proposed method: documents unavailable at the current moment of the simulation (with indexing time $T_d > t_s$) are excluded from the selection, as are non-current versions of documents according to the `is_latest` flag. The ranking of the filtered documents is performed by the RRF method, which combines the semantic and temporal ranked lists:

$$S_{RRF}(d) = \sum_{i \in R} \frac{1}{k + r_i(d)} \quad (11)$$

where:

- d — the document being scored
- R — the set of ranked lists being combined (semantic and temporal)
- $r_i(d)$ — the rank of document d in the i -th list
- k — the smoothing constant

4 Experiments

To test the put-forward hypotheses, a series of tests was conducted on an isolated server setup. The main emphasis is placed on full reproducibility.

4.1 Data and Search Configuration

Common parameters for both systems:

- To assess answer quality, a sample of 624 questions from TempRAGEval was selected, for which relevant data was guaranteed to be present in the knowledge base;
- The number of documents (top-k) retrieved by the retriever: $k = 3$;
- The minimum similarity threshold (score threshold): 0.3;
- Chunk size: the documents are too small, so they are indexed into the database in full without splitting into chunks. The average document size is ~ 500 words;
- Model for generation: gemma-4-26B-A4B-it;
- Model for time marker extraction: gemma-4-E4B-it;
- Model hyperparameters: $t = 0.1$, $top - k = 50$ and $top - p = 0.95$;

Temporally dynamic system:

- Coefficients for the temporally dynamic system: $w_1 = 0.5$, $w_2 = 0.4$;
- Simulation end time: the year 2040;
- Data update stream cycle: 5 year.

Table 1. Varied values in the parameter configuration

Parameter	Temporally static	Temporally dynamic
Data mode	Fixed array of documents	Continuous stream
Coefficient σ	—	0.1/1/2.5/5/10/20/50/100
Percentage of documents with updated indexing time per 1 simulation cycle	—	5/10/25

The results of the calculations are given in Tables No. 1 and No. 2.

5 Results

Table 2. Accuracy metrics for the temporally static system

Method	Accuracy	Temporal Accuracy	Acc@k	Latency, sec
Naive RAG (Baseline)	0.804	0.719	0.963	7.82
Timestamps Augmentation	0.782	0.751	0.963	20.94
Timestamps Filtering	0.837	0.764	0.963	20.01

Table 3. Temporal relevance metrics for the temporally dynamic system

Method	Future Leakage / Staleness Rate	Mean Temporal Error, years
Naive RAG	0.1245 / 0.4582	72.2
Metadata Filtering	0.0 / 0.0	76.9 (↑ 6.5%)
RRF Filtering Baseline	0.0 / 0.0	53.3 (↓ 26.2%)
Temporal Score Solution	0.0 / 0.0	50.6 (↓ 29.9%)

6 Conclusion

This work presented a modified architecture of the RAG system oriented toward the processing of streaming data with regard to temporal context. The main attention was paid to the problem of chronological confusion in the answers of language models, arising from the absence of mechanisms for assessing the relevance of a query in standard semantic search methods, to the development of algorithms for eliminating this problem, and to the study of the selection of parameters used in the work.

In the course of the study, the following results were achieved:

- A filtering mechanism was developed that uses a hybrid scoring function. The combination of semantic closeness and temporal intersection (S_{temp}) made it possible to effectively prioritize current documents and reduce the main metrics of the temporally dynamic system (a reduction of mean temporal error by 29.9%).

- A mechanism for extracting time markers and filtering was developed for the temporally static system, which made it possible to increase accuracy by 3%. As directions for further research, the automatic selection of the weighting coefficients σ , w_1 , and w_2 depending on the query type, and more experiments on various models, are being considered.

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